

Effect of Media Influencers on Cohesive Behaviour of Young People on Rural Area : A study in Gajraula.

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Abstract

As the scenario changing at world platform the role of media influencers are increasing day by day in determining behavior of people. Studies had confirmed its effect on marketing behavior. Current study is investigating its effect on daily behavior of young people in Gajraula. Interview method is used for data collection. Questions were related to its effect on daily routine and life style of young people. Gender wise comparison was also done to find out whether it has varied effect on behavior of male and female respondents. Result shows average effect of media influencers on daily behavior of young people, especially when it concerns to adopting the life style of influencers.

Keywords

Media, Influencers, Cohesive, Young, Rural Area, Gajraula.

Introduction

Digital platforms now a days are becoming very popular among youths. Youtube shorts or videos and reels are captivating them. Social media is becoming a powerful instrument to mobilize public in a particular direction. In 2019 this media influencer platform for marketing was estimated as 148.04 million USD and is anticipated an expansion of USD 337.74 million by the year of 2027. Influencer marketing is becoming a promising area of digital marketing field. It has a viable scope in many fields that includes healthcare, lifestyle and welfare programs (Reportlinker, 2019).

Objective of study

The study was focused on finding out the effect of media influencers on the daily life of young adults in Gajraula. It also analyzed its varied effect on male and female in their everyday life.

Review of Literature

Many studies have been conducted so far on the effect of social media influencers. Most of them were to find out its effect on marketing, determining brand value and customers purchasing preferences. These studies suggested that social media influencers have vital role in determining market strategies. Monique Potvin Kent¹, et al. (2024) conducted a study in Canada on children they found that popular influencers increasingly exposing children towards unhealthy foods.

Woods (2016) in his study on 13 employees of advertising agency tried to investigate how advertising techniques were being evolved and how they were making their strategies in current scenario specifically keeping social media influencers in their mind. The study presented a deeper insight of social media influencers affecting the advertising agencies.

Child vloggers are extremely popular; they have ample number of followers. Industries oftenly use these vloggers for their product marketing. They have a powerful impact on marketing preferences of children below 12 years of age (Marijke De Veirman , Liselot Hudders, & Michelle R. Nelson, 2019).

A survey on Gen 'y' and 'z' conducted in Slovakia on 459 participants. This study explored a varied effect of influencers on these two generation. It was suggested that industry must consider the preference of influencer for target generation to market their product (Zdenka Kádeková & Mária Holienčinová, 2018).

Social media influencers have significant effect on improving vocabulary, enhancing cultural awareness, providing intellectual engagement and help in decision-making (R,Hibaya et.al. 2024).

Methodology

40 students studying in undergraduate courses were selected for study. The age of participants was 18-24 years. Participants were selected from normal population as the study aims to find

out the effect of media influencers on general public, not on conventional followers. Interview method was used to find out the information regarding the impact of the influencers to whom they were following. The questions were based on the effect of influencers on their everyday life. Some pre interview questions were also asked to seek the basic information. Data was collected on 20 questions. Percentage of response was calculated and analyzed. Responses were obtained on two options "yes or no". Inclusion & exclusion criteria was finalized that the participant must be following an influencer and should fall between the age category of 18-24 years.

Analysis

Obtained information is given in table below:-

S.N.	Questions	% of Yes response	% of No response
1	Do you want to meet the influencer	75	25
2	Their actions seems to be real for you	67.5	32.5
3	Do you like the content they are making	75	25
4	Are you living the life as them	55	45
5	Are you impressed by their activities	67.5	32.5
6	Do you feel changes in your life due to them	70	30
7	Can you tolerate their criticism	57.5	42.5
8	Do you feel compelled to buy the product advertised by them	75	25
9	Do you buy the product advertised by them without giving it a second thought	20	80
10	Do you notice every minor incidents related to their life.	37.5	62.5
11	Do you dress up like them	25	75
12	Are you affected by their happiness and sadness	50	50

13	Do you copy their hair style	45	55
14	Are you excited to know every detail of their private life	37.5	62.5
15	Do you try to get the physique like them	37.5	62.5
16	Do you copy their way of talking	62.5	37.5
17	Do you like to talk about them	62.5	37.5
18	Do you get angry on their mistakes	50	50
19	Do you want to co-habitat with them	25	75
20	Do you like to have the cuisines as they are having	12.5	87.5
Overall percentage		49.48	

Result and Discussion

The data shown in above table gives a descriptive picture of effects of an influencer on young adults. Data shows that p=75 of total participants wanted to meet their influencer, whereas p=67.5 found their actions, which they were posting online was real and not faked. Majority of participant p=75 liked the content they were making; they did not doubt the actions being shown in that content, which increases the probability of imitating the actions. p=70 participants found it impressive and agreed that their life changed, when they started following them. Contradictorily around average number of participants (p=45) were not interested in living the life of the influencer they are following. 80% of them was not even convinced to buy the product without analyzing, advertised by them; they evaluate the utility of product on the advice given by their influencer. Majority of followers (p=62.5) did not notice all the minor incidents happening in the life of influencer. They (p=57.5) were prepared to face the criticism also, majority of the participants were ready to accept the criticism of the influencer being followed by them. They do not show any concern about their day to day life. Majority (p=62.5) of the participants like to copy their style of talking and like to discuss about them, but they don't want to live with them and not interested in their cuisines.

The graphs given below are showing gender wise data for each item.

1. Do you want to meet the influencer :

2. Their actions seems to be real for you

3. Do you like the content they are making

4. Are you living the life as them

5. Are you impressed by their activities

6. Do you feel changes in your life due to them

7. Can you tolerate their criticism

8. Do you feel compelled to buy the product advertised by them.

9. Do you buy the product advertised by them without giving it a second thought.

10. Do you notice every minor incident related to their life.

11. Do you dress up like them.

12. Are you affected by their happiness and sadness.

13. Do you copy their hair style

14. Are you excited to know every detail of their private life .

15. Do you try to get the physique like them .

16. Do you copy their way of talking

17. Do you like to talk about them

18. Do you get angry on their mistakes

19. Do you want to co-habitat with them.

20. Do you like to have the cuisines as they are having

Gender wise score analysis revealed that female participants were more affected by the influencers than male participants. More female participants p=37 than male p= 30 find their actions real, they do not consider it edited. Most of the girls (p=40) were showed their likeness in the content, whereas only p= 35 boys like the content, so in comparison to girls boys were less moved towards the content. A major difference in boys and girls attitude can be seen in the given response of item no. 11 " do you dress up like them" p=5 girls response was affirmative whereas p=20 boys agreed that they dress up like them, this may be due to the rural area where girls are not allowed to wear all kind of dresses. This major difference can also be seen in item no. 13 which is related to the copying of hair style, male participants p=30 were more likely to copy hair style than that (p= 15) of female participants. Many studies investigated a positive influence on consumer's marketing preferences whereas result of current study revealed that only 20% participants (male and female) were convinced to buy the product without analyzing it, 80% was not convinced. 37% male and 37% female participants felt compelled themselves to buy the product advertised by the media influencer whereas only 13% boys and girls did not find it impressive. This finding is in line with previous finding where a positive effect of media influencers on marketing behavior was found (Nair, Siddharth & Bhagat, Hatim.,2024).) . Similar no. p= 25 of male and female showed same level of interest in happiness and sadness related to the life of media influencers. Only p=12 of both male and female want to live with them and p=5 (boys) and p=7(Girls) want to have the same cuisine. Overall result shows that average 49.48% people are influenced by media influencers, As previous results suggested its positive correlation with marketing behavior, current study finds a positive effect of influencer's marketing preferences but this is not a blind game, they tend to analyze the product before buying. Product promoted by an influencer can make them consider it while purchasing the same items. The overall percentage is below average, which suggests that the young people residing in Gajraula were not much influenced by media influencers.

Conclusion

Above data showed that male and female had some effect of influencer on their life but this impact did not seem to have a major impact on them. Present study aims to find out the impact of these influencers on general population. With the above findings we can conclude that the effect of influencer did not have major impact on lives of general public. People watch their content for entertainment; they did not let it affect their day to day life. The result may be varied for hard core followers. People were convinced by their actions but when it comes to

apply it in their life they are very cautious, they apply their views only where they find it not challenging. Wherever there seemed any possibility of loss, they become careful, analyze the situation and then they decide. They were not easily moved by the views of the influencer.

Suggestions for the future Study

Present study opened the new paradigm for investigation. To finding the difference in attitude of general public and hard core followers a study is needed to be conducted. A comparative study can also be conducted between rural and urban young adults, which can help in planning the policies of marketing, election campaign, public awareness etc.

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